

EFFICIENT CLASSIFICATION OF DUAL PHASE STAINLESS STEEL USING DEEP NEURAL FEATURE EXTRACTION AND ENSEMBLE CNN

Mrs.K.Andal¹, Mrs.S.Sathiya², Mr.P.Sivaraj³

¹Department of Computer Science and Engineering/Research Scholar, Annamalai University,Chidambaram , India,sanandal86@gmail.com

²Department of Computer Science and Engineering /Assistant Professor, Annamalai University,Chidambaram , India, Sathiya.sep05@gmail.com

³Department of Manufacturing Engineering/ Associate Professor, Annamalai University,Chidambaram , India, cemajorsiva@gmail.com

Abstract- Supervision of welding processes is one of the most important and complicated tasks in production lines. Neural Networks have been applied for modeling and physical control processes. A novel system which allows arc-welding defect detection and classification is presented in this paper. The analysis of the plasma spectra produced during the welding process is a well-known technique to monitor the quality of the resulting weld seams. The analysis of specific emission lines and the subsequent estimation of the electronic temperature. This profile offers a direct correlation between this parameter and the corresponding weld seams. However, the automatic identification and classification of weld defects has proven to be difficult, and it is usually performed by means of statistical studies. To overcome these limitations, a new approach that allows automatic weld defect detection based on ensemble VGGNet-16 and Inception-V3Net classification process. The plasma spectra captured from the welding process is processed with deep neural feature extraction, which reduces the processing complexity, by performing a data compression in the spectral dimension. The proposed technique has been successfully checked and compared with two state of art methods such as Alexnet and Scatternet in terms of parameters such as accuracy, precision, recall and f1 score. The proposed VGG-16 based classification achieves 94.62% accuracy, 96.67% recall, 97.7% precision, 97.21% f1-score and Inception V3 achieves 96.77% accuracy, 98.89% recall, 97.80% precision, 98.34% f1-score.

Keywords – Welding defects, classification, feature extraction, Convolution Neural Network.

I. INTRODUCTION

The damage encountered in forming of metallic components poses both a great challenge in manufacturing, as well as enormous potential for improved lightweight design. Current efforts to lighten load-bearing structures, e.g. car bodies, focus on an increased use of low density materials, such as aluminium and magnesium alloys, enhancement of the (cold) formability of high strength steels and minimisation of the material used in structural elements [1]. In the context of increasing formability and improving the (remaining) local strength after processing, the key challenge is to comprehend the microstructural damage induced during deformation in metal forming [2]. This would allow engineers to minimize damage by adapting the forming processes and accurately assess the remaining material performance in service after processing to save excess material [3]. However, the physical mechanisms underlying damage in the most prominent high performance materials, such as dual-phase steels, are incompletely understood in spite of an ever-increasing research effort over the last decade [4]. The reason why the fundamental mechanisms of damage formation remain elusive lies in the complex microstructure of dual-phase steels [5]. They are categorized and marketed based only on attained yield strength and the presence of a dual phase (ferrite and martensite) microstructure, but their properties are determined by a zoo of often interdependent parameters [6].

These include volume fraction, morphology and carbon content of the hard martensite phase, mechanical contrast between the phases, homogeneity of texture, grain size and phase distribution as well as local and mesoscopic segregation of alloying elements. As in any other multiphase material that combines two components with different mechanical properties, the mechanical contrast between the constituents can induce high local strains in the microstructure. These typically exceed the macroscopic strain because the soft phase (ferrite in a dual phase steel) has to compensate for the harder phase (martensite) to maintain strain compatibility [7]. Hence, any serious endeavour to understand the damage tolerance of these materials has to account for the complex interaction of the microstructural constituents and particularly their co-deformation behaviour. In a general sense, the principal stages of damage formation include the nucleation of microscopic voids in the microstructure, and their subsequent growth

and coalescence with increasing strain until failure [8]. This process is conventionally studied post-mortem and largely manually, by analysis of samples obtained at different strains. Damage formation is, however, a dynamic phenomenon since the aforementioned stages occur and evolve depending on the microstructural environment, as well as the induced stress state. This is why in-situ techniques have become instrumental in unravelling dynamic processes as they allow researchers to observe the material deform directly and at the resolution of the chosen microscope [9]. In most cases, however, statistical relevance is sacrificed over spatial resolution by focussing only on a small area of the material to gain time- or strain-resolved information at high resolution. A further limitation is that data analysis of in-situ experiments is commonly done by hand so that larger datasets, including ones obtained post-mortem, remain difficult to analyse. To overcome these shortcomings of being limited by the field of view of a micrograph and the size of collected datasets at sufficient resolution, one has to adopt a much more powerful and efficient approach enabling 'high-throughput' ex- and in-situ analysis [10]. In the case of dual-phase steels, the pressure to achieve this, is clearly evident from the challenges still faced in unravelling damage. A vast number of studies exists from the macro- to the microscale, including a multitude of variations of the critical parameters. However, so far it has proved difficult to reconcile all observations into comprehensive descriptions and models of damage in this important engineering material [11]. We believe that the main reason lies in the heterogeneity of the microstructure, not only between samples, batches and alloys but also within each given volume of material [12].

Where the high resolution studies of deformation mechanisms are intrinsically limited by their ability to study representative areas or volumes of the investigated material [13], the transfer and comparison of results between researchers become even more difficult. A new approach is therefore essential to propel our understanding of damage in complex advanced high strength steels. Such an approach will have to combine several essential aspects: (i) imaging of deformation-induced damage mechanisms at high resolution, (ii) efficient analysis to facilitate comprehensive comparisons of material state [14] (e.g. strain level), (iii) integration of in-situ straining to observe damage evolution and (iv) quantitative analysis to the scale of a fully processed part (i.e. approaching mm² in sheet metal) to incorporate the inhomogeneous distribution of microstructural features and variable stress/strain paths encountered during forming [15]. The objective of this work is to collect the validation and testing images of dual phase SS with welded and unwelded steel and extract the features using deep neural feature extraction and to classify the extracted image using ensemble architecture of CNN with VGGNet-16 and Inception-V3Net architectures. The paper is organized as follows, section 1 explains the background of dual phase stainless steel with welding process and its properties. In the section 2 the role of deep learning and machine learning for welding classification process is explained. In section 3, the detailed methodology for feature extraction and classification is explained. Section 4 elaborately analyzed the performance analysis and then the paper ends with section 5 conclusion with future work.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Over recent years, a variety of research-based on machine learning and deep learning techniques have been conducted to establish defect diagnostics model of the steel surface with machine-vision, showing feasible performance for an automatic inspection system. For example, In [16] suggest a real-time surface defect detection method using a support vector machine (SVM) classifier, demonstrating the prediction accuracy of 85%. In [17] present feature extraction and region-based defect detection method via scale-invariant feature transform (SIFT) to enhance the accuracy with limited samples. Especially, convolutional neural network (CNN) based detection methods are widely utilized as a way of the end-to-end framework for image processing, feature learning, and classification, achieving remarkable improvement in diagnosis performance.

To take advantage of the deep learning framework, many researches have been conducted, in particular, application with CNN. A max-pooling CNN for steel defect classification is introduced in [18]. A max-pooling CNN approach is used for classifying seven different types of steel defects from a real production line. The proposed network uses supervised feature extraction directly from the steel images so that it enables to work without prior knowledge. The optimal model of the proposed one attains an error rate of 7%. Work in [19] considers an image-based method for detecting corner cracks of steel billet surface using wavelet reconstruction to reduce the influence of scales. However, its processing time requires a more considerable cost than a deep neural network-based method due to the computation of the wavelet decomposition and reconstruction.

An ensemble of support vector machine (SVM) classifiers for steel surface defects with a small sample set is introduced in [20]. Some features are obtained from a set of extractors techniques for being used as the inputs of an SVM ensemble, where a combiner, called Bayes kernel is employed to fuse the results from SVM classifiers. In [21] suggest an integrated framework with CNN and naïve Bayes data fusion scheme for detecting cracks in nuclear power plants. This work utilizes a data fusion strategy so that spatiotemporal features of the cracks in videos are efficiently used, showing improved achievement of 98.3% hit rate toward the traditional inspection system of a nuclear power plant. More recently, In [22] propose a semi-supervised approach for steel surface defect recognition based on CNN. The method has better performances with 17.53% improvement compared to the baselines. Also, it has been applied in a real-world detection scenario with a limited labeled dataset. Although several studies have been conducted to enhance the defect detection performance in the steel surface, there are still challenging issues for practical use, which motivates this study.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The general framework of the method proposed in this research is shown in Figure 1. This article is organized from the stainless steel welding and unwelding classification with the initialization of image preprocessing method. How to get the defect images rapidly and accurately is something that we need to consider in these two steps. In the image preliminary preprocessing step, effective region extraction and classification among hot round steel surface images. In the process of effective region extraction, the deep neural network is constructed to reduce the processing time.

3.1 Dataset description

This paper utilizes three Resistance Spot Welding (RSW) quality datasets. The datasets are collected from a welding data repository, which had been accumulated over many years by performing physical testing conducted by welding engineers. In total, three welding datasets include 3,573 welding cases. A response parameter included in this dataset is the nugget width. Each of these datasets includes two feature types (i.e., design and process) of RSW parameters. The design parameters represent the weldment design conditions. The process parameters represent the weld schedule used for these two material sets. The dataset includes 11 input parameters (for both materials) and one response parameter as a welding quality measure (i.e., nugget width). The nugget width is expressed in millimeters. The data includes various advanced high strength steel material including DP600 and DP780, high-strength, low-alloy steel (HSLA), and dual phase (DP) steel, etc. The specific material names are not exposed due to the confidentiality.

3.2 Preprocessing

Stainless steel preprocessing includes image enhancement and denoising. The former is implemented through calculating gray coefficient in space domain and correcting image transformation coefficient followed by inverse transformation to highlight image defects. The latter aims at suppressing impulsive noises and salt-and-pepper noises and mitigating image blurring; meanwhile, important structures in the image should be preserved. Gray level is the core of image accuracy and sensitivity of heterogeneity detection. The higher the gray level resolution of the image is, the richer the image information is, the more favorable to the classification.

The Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) of a single frame

$$SNR = \frac{xs}{\sigma n} \tag{1}$$

xs is the image signal, xn is the noise, and σn is the variance of xn.

The frame accumulated SNR is

$$SNR = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m xsi}{\sum_{i=1}^m xni} \tag{2}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^m xni = m \sigma n \tag{3}$$

$$SNR = \frac{m xs}{m \sigma n} = Msnr \tag{4}$$

The SNR is m times higher than before.

The essence of image blurring is that the image is subjected to an averaging or integral operation, so it can be restored by an inverse operation. The differential operation can highlight the image details to make the image clearer; the second-order differential edge positioning ability is stronger and the sharpening effect is better than the first-order differential. And the basic method of using the second-order differential operator is to define a discrete form of second-order differential, then generate a filter template based on this form to convolve with the image. Isotropic filter, its response is independent of the direction of the abrupt change of the image, which is the rotation invariance. Consequently, when the original image is rotated by 90°, the details (mutations) that can be detected at a certain point in the original image can also be detected after the rotation.

3.3 Multidimensional feature extraction layer

The steel welding and unwelding part extraction are affected by some complicated parameters, which consists of hot bags, gas tungsten parts and rays effects. And the performance of a data driven model highly depends on its input dataset. Therefore, the multi-dimensional feature extraction layer is proposed as the first layer of our model. From the attribute dimension, this layer can select the most correlated variables to the defect identification track. From the temporal dimension, this layer can analyze the most correlated time range to the target timestamp. The objective of this layer is to reduce the dimension of input variables and remove irrelevant noise data, which can improve the prediction accuracy and efficiency in the following layers. Here, Auto Correlation Function (ACF) and Partial Auto Correlation Function (PACF) are conducted to determine the best time range. In statistics, the autocorrelation of a random process is the Pearson Correlation (PC) between values of the process at different times. The PCC of the first $N - k$ values $L1 = \{lt1; lt2, \dots, lt(N-k)\}$ and the last $N - k$ values $L2 = \{ltk, lt(kC1), \dots, ltN\}$ is calculated by Equation

$$B1 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N-K} (li-L1)(li+k-L2)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{N-K} (li-L1)} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{N-K} (li-L2)}} \tag{5}$$

where $L1$ and $L2$ are mean of the last $N-k$ values and the last $N - k$ values, respectively. If ignoring the difference between $L1$ and $L2$, the formula of autocorrelation coefficient at time lag k can be shown in Equation

$$ACF = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N-K} (li-L1)(li+k-L1)}{(li-L1)^2} \tag{6}$$

Given the steel defects tracks $L = \{lt1, lt2, \dots, ltm\}$ the partial autocorrelation coefficient of time lag k refers to the influence of $lt-k$ on lt after removing $k - 1$ random variables. The math formula of PACF is shown in Equation

$$PACF = \frac{E [(lt - E lt)(lt - k - E lt - k)]}{E [lt - k - E lt - k]} \tag{7}$$

After implementing the multi-dimensional feature selection layer, the original features $F = \{f1, f2, \dots, fc\}$ will become $F' = \{f1, f2, \dots, fd\}$ where $(d \leq c)$, and the most correlated time range k is selected as well.

3.4 CNN-GRU layer

In the second layer, the steel defects and selected meteorological variables are used as input to the CNN model for classification which is shown in figure 2. Moreover, to improve the training efficiency and accuracy, data normalization is used to process the input data before training the CNN model.

$$Xi' = xi - \mu d / nd \tag{8}$$

where xi is the input value of location or meteorological variables, n refers to the dataset size, d is the mean of one variable, μd is the variance of one variable and xi' is normalized data. Then these normalized matrices are used as input to the CNN layer.

The mathematical formula of the convolution operation in layer l is shown as below

$$Cj = f (\sum_{mi \in M} mi \times kj + bj) \tag{9}$$

where K_j ($j=1,2,\dots,F1$) are the convolution kernel and bias of j -th convolution kernel, respectively. And f is the activation function. $F1$ is the convolution kernel size of this convolution layer. $F1$ convolution kernels can produce $F1$ feature maps.

The pooling process in layer l is shown in Equation 10

$$S_j = \beta_j \text{down}(c_j) + b_j \tag{10}$$

where β_j ($j=1,2,\dots,F1$) is the multiplicative bias of j -th pooling, $\text{down}()$ is the subsampling operation and b_j is the bias. The loss function of the CNN model uses the mean squared error with $L2$ normal, shown in Equation (10), where $L_i, tk = \{w_{el}(i,tk); u_{well}(i,tk)\}$ are observed values and fitted values of CNN at timestamp tk of stainless steel i respectively. M is the amount of training data. And $L2$ regularization constraint is added to prevent the over fitting problem

3.5 Ensemble CNN classification

We retrained two CNN models in our experiment: VGG-16 and Inception-v3. it uses 13 convolutional layers and 3 fully connected layers. The convolutional layers in VGG-16 are all 3×3 convolutional layers with a stride size of 1 and the same padding, and the pooling layers are all 2×2 pooling layers with a stride size of 2. The default input image size of VGG-16 is 224×224 . After each pooling layer, the size of the feature map is reduced by half. The last feature map before the fully connected layers is 7×7 with 512 channels and it is expanded into a vector with 25,088 ($7 \times 7 \times 512$) channels. There were three types of Inception modules in the Inception-v3 model, (Inception modules A, B and C). The Inception modules are well-designed convolution modules that both generate discriminatory features and reduce parameters. Each Inception module is composed of several convolutional and pooling layers in parallel. Small convolutional layers (e.g., 3×3 , 1×3 , 3×1 , and 1×1) are used in the Inception modules to reduce the number of parameters. Inception-v3 stacks 3 Inception A, 5 Inception B and 2 Inception C modules in series. The default input image size for the VGG-16 model is 229×229 . After the convolutional and Inception modules, the resulting feature map is 8×8 with 2,048 channels. We used a global pooling layer before the fully connected layer

The proposed ensemble learning framework involves multiple levels of fusion of diverse classifiers trained on different feature sets. Also, the feature set extracted using a specific method can be further processed to obtain different feature subsets using different feature selection methods. In the third layer, about training of multiple classifiers, machine learning algorithms are used to train base classifiers on each feature set F_i , therefore, a primary ensemble E_i is created on each of the n feature sets as shown in the primary fusion layer. Finally, the n primary ensembles created on the n feature sets are fused further to create the final ensemble, so that a final classification is made as the output of the final ensemble as shown in the final fusion layer.

We first define the cross-validated loss for j th base learner

$$R_{cv} = \sum_{v=1}^V \sum_{i \in \text{val}(v)} l(y_i, p_{ij}) \tag{11}$$

where $\text{val}(v)$ is the set of indices of the observations in the v th fold and p_{ij} is defined as the prediction for the i th observation, from the j th base learner that trained on the whole data except the v th fold.

For simplicity, we consider the binary classification task, which could be easily generalized to multi-class classification and regression. We first study a simple version of the Super Learner with m single algorithms, using negative (Bernoulli) log-likelihood as loss function.

$$l(y, p) = - [y \log(p) + (1-y) \log(1-p)] \tag{12}$$

$$R_{cv(a)} = \sum_{v=1}^V \sum_{i \in \text{val}(v)} [y_i \log(\sum_{j=1}^m a_j p_{ji}) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \sum_{j=1}^m a_j p_{ji})] \tag{13}$$

where p_{ji} is the predicted probability for i th unit from j th base learner which is trained on the whole data except v th fold.

For K -class classification with softmax output like neural networks, we could also ensemble in the score level:

$$P_i(a) = \frac{\exp(\sum_{j=1}^m a_j s_{j,z})}{\sum_{k=1}^K \exp(\sum_{j=1}^m a_j s_{j,k})} \tag{14}$$

where $p_z i(a)$ is the ensemble prediction for i th unit and z th class with weight vector a . s_i is an m by K matrix and $s_{j,k}$ stands for the score of j th model and k th class.

3.6 Algorithm

Input: selected stainless steel features

Output: Classified defects with welded and unwelded parts

MF() ← Multivariate Function

Target ← Initialize Target Vector

Base = Target Vector + Random Integer

for number of iterations do

TempVector1 = Target + RandomDeviation

TempVector2 = Target - RandomDeviation

Weighted = WeightedDifference(TempVector1, TempVector2)

$$\{(y_j', x_j)\}_{j=1}^n, \text{ where } x_j = 0, 1$$

For $r=1, \dots, R$ do

standardize the weights w_r , in amount to $\sum w_r \cdot j \cdot n_j = 1$

For all feature j , train a weak classifier h_i .

For error ϵ_i of a classifier h_i is designed matching to the weight w_r, \dots, w_r, n :

$$\epsilon_i = \sum w_r \cdot j \cdot |h_i(y_j') - x_j| \cdot n_j = 1$$

Base = Base + Weighted

Trial = Aggregate(Target, Base)

if MF(Trial) < MF(Base) then

Base = Trial

else

Base = Target

end if

end for

return Base

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the experiment, the entire data set is randomly split into training, validation and testing data set, where 70% of the whole images are used as a training set whilst 20% and 10% of them are, respectively, used as testing and validation set. The main challenging issue of the described data set is confusing spatial characteristics of the images. In some cases, it is difficult to identify spatial information as it sporadically appears in different aspects of the images. The experimental result is carried out in matlab software and the parameters used for analysis are accuracy, f1-score, recall and precision. These parameters are compared with two state of art methods such as Alexnet and Scatnetnet. Table-1 shows the comparison of for parameters such as accuracy, precision, recall and f1 measure for VGG-16 net

Table-1 comparison of VGG-16 training process

Iteration	TP	TN	FP	FN	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1-score
10	84	1	5	5	89.47	94.38	94.38	94.38
20	85	1	4	5	90.52	94.44	95.5	94.97
50	87	1	2	3	94.62	96.66	97.75	97.2

Figure-1 Training process of VGG-16

The figure 1 shows the analysis of training process of VGG-16 where x axis is number of iteration and y axis indicates loss and accuracy. During the training process, there is no drastic change in accuracy and it is observed that the loss is reduced with increased number of iterations.

		Confusion Matrix		
		Quality Good	Quality Medium	
Output Class	Quality Good	7 35.0%	1 5.0%	87.5% 12.5%
	Quality Medium	2 10.0%	10 50.0%	83.3% 16.7%
		77.8% 22.2%	90.9% 9.1%	85.0% 15.0%
		Quality Good	Quality Medium	
		Target Class		

Figure-2 Confusion matrix of VGG-16

The above figure 2 shows the confusion matrix for VGG-16 classifier in which the rows represent the predicted class (output class) and columns denote the actual class (target class) of data pertaining to welding and unwelding. The diagonal green and pink denote that, they are good quality and medium quality. The column on the right side indicates every predicted class while the row at bottom represents the performance of every actual class.

Figure 3(a) Input steel image

Figure 3 (b) output good quality steel image

Figure 3(c) Input steel image

Figure 3 (d) output medium quality steel image

Figure-3 good and medium quality images using VGG-16 network

Figure-3 shows the input and output image for good and medium quality images using VGG-16 network. The output we get here are undefected images with improves overall accuracy.

Table-2 shows the comparison of for parameters such as accuracy, precision, recall and f1 measure for Inception-v3

Table-2 comparison of Inception-v3 training process

Iteration	TP	TN	FP	FN	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1-score
10	85	1	5	4	90.52	95.5	94.4	94.97
20	87	1	4	3	92.63	96.66	95.64	96.13
50	89	1	2	1	96.77	98.88	97.8	98.34

Figure-4 Training process of Inception-v3

The figure 4 shows the analysis of training process of Inception-v3 where x axis is number of iteration and y axis indicates loss and accuracy. During the training process, there is linear improvement in accuracy and it is observed that the loss is reduced in medium range for various epochs with increased number of iterations.

Figure-5 Confusion matrix of Inception-v3

The above figure 5 shows the confusion matrix for Inception-v3 classifier in which the rows represent the predicted class (output class) and columns denotes the actual class (target class) of data pertaining to welding and unwelding. The diagonal green and pink denote that, they are good quality and medium quality. The column on the right side indicates every predicted class while the row at bottom represents the performance of every actual class.

Figure 6(a) Input steel image

Figure 6(b) output good quality steel image

Figure 6(c) Input steel image

Figure 6(d) output good quality steel image

Figure-6 good and medium quality images using Inception-v3 network

Table 3: Comparison of various classification CNN networks

Method	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1-score
Inception-v3	96.77	98.89	97.80	98.34
VGG 16	94.62	96.67	97.75	97.21

Alexnet	93.36	92.59	95.18	96.36
Scatternet	90.51	91.57	92.77	94.96

Accuracy indicates the general prediction capability of the projected deep learning model. True positive (TP) and true negative (TN) compute the capacity of classifier form to calculate the lack and being there of good and medium quality. False positive (FP) and false negative (FN) recognize the amount of false predictions produce by the models.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \tag{15}$$

Figure-7 Comparison of accuracy

The figure 7 shows the accuracy calculation for various CNN classifiers where, X axis shows the methods for analysis and Y axis shows the accuracy values obtained in percentage. The existing classifiers such as Alexnet and Scatternet achieves 93.36% and 90.51% of accuracy where, the proposed Inception-v3 and VGG 16 achieves 96.77% and 94.62% of accuracy

Recall indicates the likelihood of a classifier that achieves outcome as negative at the absence of defect. It is otherwise named as true negative (TN) rate, and can be calculate as:

$$Recall (R) = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \tag{16}$$

Figure-8 Comparison of recall

The figure 8 shows the recall calculation for various CNN classifiers where, X axis shows the methods for analysis and Y axis shows the recall values obtained in percentage. The existing classifiers such as Alexnet and Scatternet achieves 92.59% and 91.57% of recall where, the proposed Inception-v3 and VGG 16 achieves 98.89% and 96.67% of recall.

Precision indicates overall achievement of the defect classification model, correspondingly. It is the likelihood of a classification function which is forecast to outcome as true positive rate at the presence of defect. It is also recognized as true positive (TP) amount and can be compute as:

$$Precision (P) = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (17)$$

Figure-9 Comparison of precision

The figure 9 shows the precision calculation for various CNN classifiers where, X axis shows the methods for analysis and Y axis shows the precision values obtained in percentage. The existing classifiers such as Alexnet and Scatternet achieves 95.18% and 92.77% of precision where, the proposed Inception-v3 and VGG 16 achieves 97.80% and 97.75% of precision.

F1- Score is exploit to establish the prediction performance. It is constructed by analyzing the harmonic part of the precision and recall. A computed score value of 1 is measured as most excellent and if it is 0, results in bad. F-measures wont consider the true negative rate in its account. The F1-Score can be calculated as:

$$F1 - Score = \frac{2 * P * R}{P + R} \tag{14}$$

Figure-10 Comparison of f1-score

The figure 10 shows the f1-score calculation for various CNN classifiers where, X axis shows the methods for analysis and Y axis shows the f1-score values obtained in percentage. The existing classifiers such as Alexnet and Scatternet achieves 96.36% and 94.96% of f1-score where, the proposed Inception-v3 and VGG 16 achieves 98.34% and 97.21% of f1-score .

V. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Figure 11 : System Architecture

VI. CONCLUSION

A deep learning-based weld defect detection and image defect recognition system is established based on summarizing previous research. This system aims to recognize major weld defects such as, inclusions, scratches, scars, roll marks, and bubbles. The fitting problem during weld defect detection is solved by image preprocessing using image denoising and enhancement. The problem of insufficient training data in DNNs is solved by applying an improved activation function adaptive pooling method to the model. The transfer learning method based on VGG-16 and Inception V3 for weld defects classification. The previously learned network architecture has been modified to fit the new classification problem by resizing the output layer and adding two dropout layers to avoid the overfitting problem. The application of the fully convolutional structure needs the same size input for training as the similar processing, even for the testing images.

Comparing the results of our network with the Alexnet and Scatternet models with transfer learning, we note that our VGG-16 and Inception V3 network achieves the highest performance. As expected, it has been verified that it is recommended to fine-tune the fully connected layers of the VGG-16 and Inception V3 network instead of doing it for the whole network, specifically for small datasets. The proposed VGG-16 based classification achieves 94.62% accuracy, 96.67% recall, 97.7% precision, 97.21% f1-score and Inception V3 achieves 96.77% accuracy, 98.89% recall, 97.80% precision, 98.34% f1-score. The future work is to improve the ensemble classification by including regression based optimized method for better results.

REFERENCES

1. Tasan CC, Diehl M, Yan D, Bechtold M, Roters F, Schemmann L, et al. An overview of dual-phase steels: advances in microstructure-oriented processing and micromechanically guided design. *Annual Review of Materials Research*. 2015;45:391–431.
2. Calcagnotto M, Adachi Y, Ponge D, Raabe D. Deformation and fracture mechanisms in fine- and ultrafine-grained ferrite/martensite dual-phase steels and the effect of aging. *Acta Materialia*. 2011;59:658–70.
3. Zhang J, Di H, Deng Y, Misra RDK. Effect of martensite morphology and volume fraction on strain hardening and fracture behavior of martensite–ferrite dual phase steel. *Materials Science and Engineering A*. 2015;627:230–40.
4. Landron C, Maire E, Bouaziz O, Adrien J, Lecarme L, Bareggi A. Validation of void growth models using X-ray microtomography characterization of damage in dual phase steels. *Acta Materialia*. 2011;59(20):7564–73.
5. Wu Z, Sandlöbes S, Wu L, Hu W, Gottstein G, Korte-Kerzel S. Mechanical behaviour of Zn–Al–Cu–Mg alloys: Deformation mechanisms of as-cast microstructures. *Materials Science and Engineering: A*. 2016;651:675–87.
6. Kim D, Kim W, Han J, Woo W, Choi S. Effect of microstructural factors on void formation by ferrite/martensite interface decohesion in DP980 steel under uniaxial tension. *International Journal of Plasticity*. 2017;94:3–23.
7. Kadkhodapour J, Butz A, Ziaei-Rad S, Schmauder S. A micro mechanical study on failure initiation of dual phase steels under tension using single crystal plasticity model. *International Journal of Plasticity*. 2011;27:1103–25.
8. Cha Y-J, Choi W, Büyüköztürk O. Deep Learning-Based Crack Damage Detection Using Convolutional Neural Networks. *Computer-Aided Civil and Infrastructure Engineering*. 2017;32(5):361–78.
9. Tasan C, Hoefnagels J, Geers M. Identification of the continuum damage parameter: An experimental challenge in modeling damage evolution. *Acta Materialia*. 2012;60(8):3581–9.
10. Archie F, Li X, Zaefferer S. Micro-damage initiation in ferrite-martensite DP microstructures: A statistical characterization of crystallographic and chemical parameters. *Materials Science and Engineering*. 2017;A 701:302–13.
11. Y. Wang, H. Guo, Weld defect detection of X-ray images based on support vector machine, *IETE Tech. Rev.* 31 (2) (2014) 137–142.
12. C.M. Bishop, *Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning*. Information Science and Statistics Series, Springer, 2006.
13. J. Shao, et al., Automatic weld defect detection based on potential defect tracking in real time sequence radiographic image sequence, *NDT & E Int.* 46 (2012) 14–21.
14. Song, K.; Yan, Y. A noise robust method based on completed local binary patterns for hot-rolled steel strip surface defects. *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 2013, 285, 858–864.

15. Suvdaa, B.; Ahn, J.; Ko, J. Steel surface defects detection and classification using SIFT and voting strategy. *Int. J. Softw. Eng. Appl.* 2012, 6, 161–166.
16. Park, J.K.; Kwon, B.K.; Park, J.H.; Kang, D.J. Machine learning-based imaging system for surface defect inspection. *Int. J. Precis. Eng. Manuf.-Green Technol.* 2016, 3, 303–310.
17. Wang, T.; Chen, Y.; Qiao, M.; Snoussi, H. A fast and robust convolutional neural network-based defect detection model in product quality control. *Int. J. Adv. Manuf. Technol.* 2018, 94, 3465–3471
18. Xian, G.M. An identification method of malignant and benign liver tumors from ultrasonography based on GLCM texture features and fuzzy SVM. *Expert Syst. Appl.* 2010, 37, 6737–6741
19. Jeon, Y.J.; Choi, D.C.; Lee, S.J.; Yun, J.P.; Kim, S.W. Defect detection for corner cracks in steel billets using a wavelet reconstruction method. *JOSA A* 2014, 31, 227–237.
20. Chen, W.; Gao, Y.; Gao, L.; Li, X. A New Ensemble Approach based on Deep Convolutional Neural Networks for Steel Surface Defect classification. *Procedia CIRP* 2018, 72, 1069–1072.
21. Gao, Y.; Gao, L.; Li, X.; Yan, X. A semi-supervised convolutional neural network-based method for steel surface defect recognition. *Robot. Comput.-Integr. Manuf.* 2020
22. Luo, Q.; He, Y. A cost-effective and automatic surface defect inspection system for hot-rolled flat steel. *Robot. Comput.-Integr. Manuf.* 2016, 38, 16–30